

FUNCTIONAL PEARL

An algorithmic reconstruction of normalisation by evaluation

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Abstract

This article demonstrates how a naive applicative-order normaliser of untyped λ -calculus can be step-by-step transformed to efficient normalisation-by-evaluation normalisers based on some elementary observations and the algorithmic trick of lazy tagging, shedding some light on the connection between normalisation by evaluation and substitution-based normalisation.

1 Introduction

In the past few years, I spent quite some time learning the *categorical glueing* technique for proving properties of programming languages, in particular, the normalisation properties of type theories and programming languages (Altenkirch et al. 1996; Coquand 2023; Fiore 2022; Kaposi et al. 2019; Sterling 2021). Those proofs can usually be done in a constructive meta-theory and it is in principle possible to extract the algorithmic content of the proof, giving us a *normaliser* that takes in programs of the object language as input and computes the normal form of the input. The normaliser works by first evaluating the input program as a value in a certain semantic domain, which can then be ‘reified’ into a normal form. This way of normalising programs is called *normalisation by evaluation* (NbE).

Normalisation by evaluation is known to be more efficient in practice than substitution-based normalisers. Glueing proofs nicely explains *why normalisation by evaluation is correct*, but I find that they do not tell me much about *why normalisation by evaluation is fast*. In this article, I hope to shed some light on the latter question by showing how we can spot the sources of inefficiency in a naive substitution-based normaliser, optimise these inefficiency problems with some standard algorithmic tricks, and eventually obtain NbE. In fact, through this process we will also see some inefficiency problems in NbE, and in the end we will end up with a normaliser that is *asymptotically better* than a standard NbE normaliser on some input programs (and never worse on any input).

The way this article is written is inspired by the calculational approach of the School of Squiggol (Gibbons 2020). However, I will only informally justify each step of transforming our normalisers without proper equational proofs. I believe the missing proofs can be supplied in principle, but this article is already longer than I wish for a functional pearl, so let us regard it as the shell of an unusually large pearl.

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2 Preliminary setup: lambda terms

We will use Haskell as our meta-language. Haskell is lazy by default. Although laziness never harms the time complexity of programs (and can sometimes make asymptotic improvements!), reasoning about running cost when everything is lazy is a nightmare. Therefore we will turn on the `Strict` extension of GHC, which makes laziness an *opt-in* feature (by decorating binding variables or constructor fields with `~`) rather than the default behaviour. Enabling `Strict` also makes porting the code in this article to strict programming languages (say, C or OCaml) a lot easier, as there is no implicit laziness that our algorithms secretly rely on.

Note however, `Strict` does not change the behaviour of existing definitions from other modules, such as those from `Prelude`, so the built-in list type `[a]` remains to be lazy lists of lazy payloads. Let us define a type synonym to remind us of this:

```
type LazyList a = [a]
```

If we want strict lists, we can define our own `data List a = Nil | Cons a (List a)` in this module (or any other module with `Strict` enabled).

Since our topic is about the *efficiency* rather than the *correctness* of NbE, we will simply use untyped lambda calculus as our object language in this article. Consequently, our normalisers will not terminate on input programs that do not have a normal form, and we are only interested in programs that do have normal forms.

We will use *de Bruijn indices* to represent variables formally (but we will still use named variables in our informal discussion). The following code is some basic definitions for the syntax of lambda calculus using de Bruijn indices, and the reader is assumed to be familiar with them (de Bruijn 1972; Pierce 2002).

```
data Tm = Var Int | App Tm Tm | Abs Tm
```

For visual clarity, we will sometimes write application `App f x` as the infix operator `f · x`.

The function `subst s v t` substitutes `t` for every occurrence of `v` in `s`:

```
subst :: Tm -> Int -> Tm -> Tm
subst (Var n) v t = if v == n then t else Var n
subst (App f a) v t = App (subst f v t) (subst a v t)
subst (Abs b) v t = Abs (subst b (v + 1) (shift 0 1 t))
```

The function `shift x i t` adds an integer `i` to all the free variables of `t` that are $\geq x$:

```
shift :: Int -> Int -> Tm -> Tm
shift x 0 t = t
shift x i (Var n) = if n >= x then Var (n + i) else Var n
shift x i (App f a) = App (shift x i f) (shift x i a)
shift x i (Abs b) = Abs (shift (x + 1) i b)
```

The function `beta b a` does β -reduction for $(\lambda x. b) a$. Because `b` lives in one level deeper than `a`, we use `shift 0 1` to bring `a` to the same level of `b`. Also after substitution, we want to remove the λ -abstraction, so we need to do `shift 0 (-1)` for the result of substitution.

```
beta :: Tm -> Tm -> Tm
beta b a = shift 0 (-1) (subst b 0 (shift 0 1 a))
```

The function $fv\ t$ computes the biggest de Bruijn index of all free variables in a term t . If a term has no free variables, the result is -1 .

$$\begin{aligned} fv &:: Tm \rightarrow Int \\ fv\ (Var\ n) &= n \\ fv\ (Abs\ b) &= \max\ (-1)\ (fv\ b - 1) \\ fv\ (App\ f\ a) &= \max\ (fv\ f)\ (fv\ a) \end{aligned}$$

To pretty print a lambda term, we use a function $showTm\ ns\ t$ to compute both the string representation of a term and the precedence of the outermost syntactic constructor. A variable has the highest precedence 100, application has the precedence 50, and abstraction has the lowest precedence 0. The argument ns of $showTm$ is the current de Bruijn level.

instance Show Tm where

$$\begin{aligned} show\ t &= \mathbf{let}\ n = fv\ t\ \mathbf{in}\ fst\ (showTm\ (n + 1)\ t) \\ showTm &:: Int \rightarrow Tm \rightarrow (String, Int) \\ showTm\ ns\ (Var\ n) &= ("x" ++ show\ (ns - n - 1), 100) \\ showTm\ ns\ (Abs\ b) &= \mathbf{let}\ (s, _) = showTm\ (ns + 1)\ b \\ &\quad \mathbf{in}\ ("\\x" ++ show\ ns ++ ". " ++ s, 0) \\ showTm\ ns\ (App\ f\ a) &= \mathbf{let}\ (s_1, p_1) = showTm\ ns\ f \\ &\quad (s_2, p_2) = showTm\ ns\ a \\ &\quad s'_1 = \mathbf{if}\ p_1 \geq 50\ \mathbf{then}\ s_1\ \mathbf{else}\ "(" ++ s_1 ++ ")" \\ &\quad s'_2 = \mathbf{if}\ p_2 > 50\ \mathbf{then}\ s_2\ \mathbf{else}\ "(" ++ s_2 ++ ")" \\ &\quad \mathbf{in}\ (s'_1 ++ " " ++ s'_2, 50) \end{aligned}$$

As an example of the pretty printer, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \ggg\ Abs\ (Var\ 0 \cdot Var\ 0) \cdot (Abs\ (Var\ 0)) \cdot (Abs\ (Var\ 0)) \\ (\backslash x0. x0\ x0)\ (\backslash x0. x0)\ (\backslash x0. x0) \end{aligned}$$

3 Applicative-order normalisation

Now let us start with a simple-minded normaliser. We would like to define a function

$$nf_0 :: Tm \rightarrow Tm$$

that takes in an arbitrary lambda term, which is allowed to have free variables, and should produce a normal form β -equivalent to the input. Recall that the definition of a term t being in normal form is given inductively as follows.

Definition 3.1. A lambda term t is in normal form if

- (1) t is a variable applied to zero or more arguments, where each argument is in normal form, i.e. $t = v\ a_1\ a_2 \cdots a_n$ where v is a variable, $n \geq 0$, and each a_i is in normal form (the base case of a normal form is when $n = 0$), or
- (2) t is a λ -abstraction applied to a normal form, i.e. $t = \lambda x. b$ where b is in normal form.

When the input to nf_0 is a variable, we are already done:

$$nf_0\ (Var\ n) = Var\ n$$

When the input is a λ -abstraction, we can just recursively compute the normal form of the function body:

205 The last point about why we do not want to fully normalise the function f actually is
 206 another reason why we do not want to normalise the argument a , because in the function
 207 body of f , the argument a may be used as a function as well! For example, consider the term
 208

$$209 \quad (\lambda y. y (\lambda z. M)) (\lambda x. x \text{ExpensiveTm})$$

210 In $\lambda y. y (\lambda z. M)$, the argument y is not unused, but we still do not want to fully normalise
 211 its concrete argument $\lambda x. x \text{ExpensiveTm}$ before substituting it for y , because the argument
 212 $(\lambda x. x \text{ExpensiveTm})$ will be used as a function after substitution.
 213

214 From the observation above, we see that the problem with nf_0 is that when it sees a function
 215 application $f a$, it may too eagerly normalise f and a . If we want to fix this inefficiency, what
 216 is the minimum amount of normalisation work that we should do to f and a instead?

- 217 (1) We must at least normalise f to expose its outermost λ -abstraction, because that is
 218 what we need for doing a β -reduction. We can normalise f more, but exposing its
 219 outermost layer is the minimum requirement. In jargon, we must at least normalise f
 220 to its *weak head normal form* (WHNF).
 221
- 222 (2) We have no constraints on how much normalisation to do for a . We can leave it totally
 223 unnormalised when supplying it to the function, or we can also normalise it to expose
 224 the outermost λ -abstraction, or we can fully normalise it as we did in nf_0 .

225 For the function f , doing the minimum amount of work (i.e. normalising f to its WHNF) is
 226 optimal. To see this, suppose the WHNF of f is $(\lambda x. M)$. In the term M , the variable x may
 227 be used both as a function and as an argument, so M looks like $\dots(x M_1) \dots (M_2 x)\dots$. By
 228 substituting (a possibly partially normalised form of) the argument a for x before normalising
 229 this function body M , we may be able to avoid normalising M_1 if a does not use M_1 . And
 230 substituting a in before normalising M_2 does not create any additional overhead either.
 231

232 On the other hand, how much we normalise the argument a before supplying it to the
 233 function is more interesting: As we said before, full normalisation is not optimal because in
 234 the function body a may be unused or it may be used as a function. Doing no normalisation
 235 at all is a bad idea too because the argument of f may occur multiple times in f . Substituting
 236 unnormalised a for each of these occurrences leads us to duplicate normalisation work for a .
 237

238 A third choice is to normalise the argument a to *the same extent as f* , since the argument a
 239 may be used as a function inside f as well. A precise way to describe this choice is that we
 240 first compute *weak normal forms* (WNFs) of terms in the process of full normalisation.

241 *Definition 4.1.* A term is in *weak normal form* if it is either

- 242 (1) a λ -abstraction, or
- 243 (2) a variable applied to zero or more arguments that are weak normal forms themselves.
 244

245 Moreover, we can weakly normalise the function argument a lazily, so that if the function
 246 body of f does not actually use its argument, the work of weakly normalising a can be saved.
 247 Although we will see later that this strategy has its own problems too, it is a pretty decent
 248 one, so let us carry it out now.
 249

250 5 Weak-applicative-order normalisation

251 Following our plan, let us define a new function $wnf_1 :: Tm \rightarrow Tm$ for normalising a term to
 252 WNF. The way this function works is similar to nf_0 : when we see an application, we reduce
 253 the function and the argument to WNF, and if the WNF of the function is a λ -abstraction, we
 254
 255

256 do a β -reduction and re-normalise to WNF. The difference from nf_0 is that when wnf_1 sees a
 257 λ -abstraction, it does nothing (whereas nf_0 would continue to normalise under the binder).

258
 259 $wnf_1 :: Tm \rightarrow Tm$
 260 $wnf_1 (App\ f\ a) = \mathbf{let}\ f' = wnf_1\ f; \ \sim a' = wnf_1\ a$
 261 $\qquad\qquad\qquad \mathbf{in\ case}\ f' \ \mathbf{of}\ Abs\ b \rightarrow wnf_1\ (beta_L\ b\ a')$
 262 $\qquad\qquad\qquad \qquad\qquad\qquad \rightarrow App\ f'\ a'$
 263
 264 $wnf_1\ t = t$

265 Note that the variable a' is annotated with \sim , which makes a' lazily evaluated (if b does not
 266 use its argument, $a' = wnf_1\ a$ will not be computed). We also need to use a version of $beta$
 267 that is lazy in its second argument. Until someone designs ‘strictness polymorphism’ and
 268 implements it in GHC, we have no choice but to duplicate our $beta$ and $subst$ functions with
 269 a \sim annotation in the arguments that we would like to be lazy:

270
 271 $beta_L :: Tm \rightarrow Tm \rightarrow Tm$
 272 $beta_L\ b\ \sim a = shift\ 0\ (-1)\ (subst_L\ b\ 0\ (shift\ 0\ 1\ a))$
 273
 274 $subst_L :: Tm \rightarrow Int \rightarrow Tm \rightarrow Tm$
 275 $subst_L\ (Var\ n)\ x\ \sim t = \mathbf{if}\ x \equiv n \ \mathbf{then}\ t \ \mathbf{else}\ Var\ n$
 276 $subst_L\ (App\ f\ a)\ x\ \sim t = App\ (subst_L\ f\ x\ t)\ (subst_L\ a\ x\ t)$
 277 $subst_L\ (Abs\ b)\ x\ \sim t = Abs\ (subst_L\ b\ (x + 1)\ (shift\ 0\ 1\ t))$

278 For example, $beta_L\ (Abs\ (Var\ 0))\ \mathit{undefined}$ computes $\backslash\mathbf{x}0$. $\mathbf{x}0$ while with $beta$ it diverges.

279 Our new function for full normalisation then uses wnf_1 to compute weak normal forms in
 280 the case of a function application:

281
 282 $nf_1 :: Tm \rightarrow Tm$
 283 $nf_1\ (Var\ n) = Var\ n$
 284 $nf_1\ (Abs\ b) = Abs\ (nf_1\ b)$
 285 $nf_1\ (App\ f\ a) = \mathbf{let}\ f' = wnf_1\ f; \ \sim a' = wnf_1\ a$
 286 $\qquad\qquad\qquad \mathbf{in\ case}\ f' \ \mathbf{of}\ Abs\ b \rightarrow nf_1\ (beta_L\ b\ a')$
 287 $\qquad\qquad\qquad \qquad\qquad\qquad \rightarrow App\ (reify_1\ f')\ (reify_1\ a')$
 288

289 When the weak normal form f' of the function is not a λ -abstraction, we need to turn the
 290 weak normal forms f' and a' into (full) normal forms. This is done by the following function
 291 that triggers normalisation under λ -abstractions:

292
 293 $reify_1 :: Tm \rightarrow Tm$
 294 $reify_1\ (Var\ v) = Var\ v$
 295 $reify_1\ (Abs\ b) = Abs\ (reify_1\ (wnf_1\ b))$
 296 $reify_1\ (App\ f\ a) = App\ (reify_1\ f)\ (reify_1\ a)$
 297

298 One thing to notice is that an alternative definition of nf_1 is to simply put $nf_1 = reify_1 \circ wnf_1$.
 299 The explicit definition nf_1 above is the fused version of these two functions composed
 300 together. The fused version nf_1 is slightly more efficient than nf'_1 because it avoids building
 301 the intermediate weak normal form built by wnf_1 and consumed by $reify_1$. Deriving the fused
 302 normalising function from wnf_1 and $reify_1$ is usually not difficult (Hinze et al. 2011), so in
 303 the rest of this article we will focus on optimising wnf_1 and $reify_1$ and define normalisation
 304 as their composition.
 305
 306

To see the improvement of our new normaliser nf_1 over nf_0 , let us construct a term $(\lambda x. x \text{ expensiveTm}) (\lambda x. c_0)$ and let expensiveTm be the conjunction of a large number of Church Boolean values of truth.

```

expensiveTm :: Int → Tm
expensiveTm n = Abs (cNum n · (cAnd · cTrue) · cTrue)
cNum :: Int → Tm
cNum n = foldr (λ _ r → cinc · r) c0 [1..n]
cTrue, cFalse, cAnd :: Tm
cTrue = Abs (Abs (Var 1))
cFalse = Abs (Abs (Var 0))
cAnd = Abs (Abs (Abs (Abs (Var 3 · (Var 2 · Var 1 · Var 0) · Var 0))))

```

This takes a lot of time to compute on my machine:

$$nf_0 \$ (Abs (Var 0 \cdot \text{expensiveTm } 10000)) \cdot Abs \ c_0$$

while this takes less than a second to compute on my machine:

$$nf_1 \$ (Abs (Var 0 \cdot \text{expensiveTm } 10000)) \cdot Abs \ c_0$$

Great, our optimisation works (at least for this term)! We may call nf_1 *weak-applicative-order normalisation with meta-level laziness*. Meta-level laziness refers to the fact that function arguments are reduced lazily through the laziness of our meta-language, Haskell.

6 The lazy tagging trick

The function wnf_1 above uses the function beta to substitute the actual argument a' for the binder of the λ -abstraction. Recall that the function beta is defined by

$$\text{beta } b \ a = \text{shift } 0 \ (-1) \ (\text{subst } b \ 0 \ (\text{shift } 0 \ 1 \ a))$$

So $\text{beta } b \ a$ is not a cheap operation. We need to first use shift to bring the argument a to the next de Bruijn level, then traverse the function body b to do the actual substitution, and then use shift again to bring the result back to the previous de Bruijn level.

Can we do capture-avoiding substitution without the cost of traversing the term? A general solution to this is not easy, but here because of some special property of how wnf_1 works, we actually do not need a general solution. A very common algorithmic trick suffices.

The trick that we are going to use to make substitution efficient is *lazy tagging*. The trick is best explained by a simple example. Suppose we have a binary tree storing integers

```
data Tree = Leaf Int | Node Tree Tree
```

and suppose that we would like to perform the operation of adding some integer to every integer stored in a tree:

```

add :: Int → Tree → Tree
add n (Leaf i)  = Leaf (n + i)
add n (Node l r) = Node (add n l) (add n r)

```

The operation $\text{add } n \ t$ works in time $O(\text{size } t)$. The trick of lazy tagging optimises add to $O(1)$ by changing the tree datatype to

358 **data** $Tree' = Leaf' Int \mid Node' Int Tree' Tree'$

359 where the constructor $Node$ now has an additional Int field (the lazy tag) storing a number
 360 that has been logically added to all the leaves of the tree, but has not been added physically.
 361 With this additional field, add can be implemented as
 362

363 $add' :: Int \rightarrow Tree' \rightarrow Tree'$
 364 $add' n (Leaf' i) = Leaf' (n + i)$
 365 $add' n (Node' m l r) = Node' (n + m) l r$
 366

367 On the other hand, whenever we want to access the two sub-trees of a node, we should always
 368 push down the lazy tag first:
 369

370 $push :: Tree' \rightarrow Tree'$
 371 $push (Node' m l r) \mid m \neq 0 = Node' 0 (add' m l) (add' m r)$
 372 $push t = t$
 373

374 This $push$ operation is also $O(1)$ because add' is $O(1)$, so having an additional $push$ whenever
 375 we want to pattern match a $Node'$ does not change the time complexity. For example, if we
 376 want to sum the integers of a tree, we do
 377

378 $sumTree :: Tree' \rightarrow Int$
 379 $sumTree (Leaf' i) = i$
 380 $sumTree t = \mathbf{case} \text{ push } t \mathbf{ of Node' } _ l r \rightarrow sumTree l + sumTree r$
 381

382 In Haskell, we can even use *view patterns* and *pattern synonyms* (Pickering et al. 2016) to
 383 make the use of $push$ completely transparent.

384 The reader might be wondering how lazy tagging is different from laziness of Haskell?
 385 Why do not we simply make our trees lazy by writing
 386

387 **data** $Tree'' = Leaf'' Int \mid Node'' \sim Tree'' \sim Tree''$

388 The key difference is this line: $add' n (Node' m l r) = Node' (n + m) l r$, which combines
 389 two lazy tags n and m into one tag $n + m$. In comparison, lazy evaluation of Haskell is not
 390 clever enough to do this; after applying add for $Tree''$ a few times, we would have nested
 391 thunks $add\ n_1 (add\ n_2 (\dots (add\ n_m\ t)))$, for which we need $O(m)$ rather than $O(1)$ time to
 392 push these added integers one level down.
 393

394 7 Weak-applicative-order normalisation with lazy substitutions

396 Coming back to wnf_1 , we would like to use lazy tagging to make substitution more efficient.
 397 Just like the add example above, when we want to substitute an argument for the binder
 398 variable in a function body, we will just lazily *remember* this substitution at the root of the
 399 syntax tree without actually performing the substitution.
 400

401 Moreover, recall that our wnf_1 only normalises a function body when we have a concrete
 402 value for the function argument. Consequently, if there are two variables x and y in a term
 403 such that y is bound in the scope of x , such as in

404 $(\lambda x. \dots (\lambda y. \dots x \dots) N \dots) M$
 405

406 the variable x always receives its concrete value ($wnf_1 M$ for the term above) before y receives
 407 its concrete value ($wnf_1 N$ for the term above). Therefore we can simply represent a lazy
 408

substitution applied to a term as a list of terms. More precisely, we will store a substitution

$$(((t[a_1/x_1])[a_2/x_2])[a_3/x_3]) \dots [a_N/x_N])$$

as a pair of the original term t and the list $[a_N, \dots, a_3, a_2, a_1]$. Applying a new substitution (for the de Bruijn index 0) is just cons-ing a value to the head of the list.

Notice the correctness of this representation hinges on the fact that we are doing *capture-avoiding substitution from the outside in*. When we substitute a value a_N for a bound variable x_N , we can just cons a_N to the list $[a_{N-1}, \dots, a_2, a_1]$ of existing substitutions for the outer bound variables because we know for sure that x_N does not occur in the arguments $[a_{N-1}, \dots, a_2, a_1]$ from *outer levels*. For example, consider the term

$$(\lambda x. \dots (\lambda y. \dots x \dots) N \dots) M$$

We first substitute $wnf_1 M$ for x and then later substitute $wnf_1 N$ for y . We know for sure that y does not occur in $wnf_1 M$ because our substitution is capture avoiding. Therefore the lazy substitution for the inner function body can just be $[wnf_1 N, wnf_1 M]$, which means that variable of de Bruijn index 0 (i.e. y) has been substituted by $wnf_1 N$, the variable of de Bruijn index 1 (i.e. x) has been substituted by $wnf_1 M$.

Remark. In modal type theory, there is a concept called *delayed substitution* (Bizjak et al. 2016) for dealing with type formers that do not commute with substitutions. There is similarity between delayed substitution and our idea here, but the motivation is completely different: there the problem is that some syntactic constructors do not commute with substitution, whereas our syntactic constructors do commute with substitution and we delay substitution for efficiency considerations.

Enough with talking, let us implement our ideas. The first thing that we are going to do is to define the type of weak normal forms with lazy substitutions. Previously, wnf_1 has type $Tm \rightarrow Tm$, but now we want to work with lazy substitutions, so the output type cannot be Tm anymore (the input term can still be Tm). We need to define a new type for the output of wnf_1 . The name ‘weak normal forms with lazy substitutions’ is too verbose, so we will just call them *values*. A value is either

- (1) a λ -function, represented by $Closure_2$ below, which has two fields: the function body and the lazy substitution applied to this function (stored as a lazy list of values); or
- (2) a variable applied to a list of arguments, represented by $Spine_2$ above, which also has two fields: the de Bruijn index of the variable and the arguments (also stored as a lazy list of values).

data $Val_2 = Closure_2 Tm Subst_2 \mid Spine_2 Int (LazyList Val_2)$

type $Subst_2 = LazyList Val_2$

Here we use lazy lists (which is just the default Haskell list type $[a]$) rather than strict lists because we want to make normalisation of function arguments lazy, like how we did in wnf_1 . Strictly speaking we only need the payloads of the list to be lazy and the structure of the list itself can remain strict:

data $PayloadLazyList a = Nil \mid Cons \sim a (PayloadLazyList a)$

but let us just use *LazyList* (lazy lists of lazy payloads) because I am too lazy to re-define the standard list functions that we are going to use.

The type of $wnf_1 :: Tm \rightarrow Tm$ becomes then

$$wnf_2 :: Tm \rightarrow Subst_2 \rightarrow Val_2$$

where the output is a value (a weak normal form with lazy substitutions) and the input is a term paired with a lazy substitution applied to this term. Whenever wnf_2 sees a variable, the variable logically has been replaced by the corresponding value from the lazy substitution, so we just look up the substitution:

$$wnf_2 (Var\ n)\ sub = sub\ !!\ n$$

When wnf_2 sees a λ -abstraction, it is already a weak normal form, so we just store it along with the lazy substitution:

$$wnf_2 (Abs\ b)\ sub = Closure_2\ b\ sub$$

The interesting case is again function application $App\ f\ a$. We can do recursion on f and a

$$\begin{aligned} wnf_2 (App\ f\ a)\ sub &= \mathbf{let}\ f' = wnf_2\ f\ sub; \ \sim a' = wnf_2\ a\ sub \\ &\quad \mathbf{in\ case}\ f' \ \mathbf{of}\ Closure_2\ b\ sub' \rightarrow _ \quad \mathbf{--}\ \mathbf{what\ do\ we\ do\ here?} \\ &\quad Spine_2\ v\ as \rightarrow Spine_2\ v\ (a' : as) \end{aligned}$$

but what should we do this time when the function is a λ -abstraction? Previously we did $wnf_1 (beta\ b\ a')$ where

$$beta\ b\ a = shift\ 0\ (-1)\ (subst\ b\ 0\ (shift\ 0\ 1\ a))$$

Substituting a' for the variable 0 in b should now be just $a' : sub'$. However, we now need to shift the de Bruijn indices of the whole substitution by 1 rather than just a , because sub' is a lazy substitution applied to $Abs\ b$ rather than b . Therefore our new substitution for b should be $shift0List\ 1\ (a' : sub')$ where

$$\begin{aligned} shift0Val &:: Int \rightarrow Val_2 \rightarrow Val_2 \\ shift0Val\ i\ (Spine_2\ n\ as) &= Spine_2\ (n + i)\ (shift0List\ i\ as) \\ shift0Val\ i\ (Closure_2\ b\ sub) &= Closure_2\ b\ (shift0List\ i\ sub) \\ shift0List &:: Int \rightarrow Subst_2 \rightarrow Subst_2 \\ shift0List\ i &= map\ (shift0Val\ i) \end{aligned}$$

Note that $shift0Val$ does not need to shift the indices in the function body b , because these variables have logically already been substituted by sub .

Another difficulty is the $shift\ 0\ (-1)$ in the definition of $beta\ b\ a$. Because now our substitution is lazy, we do not really have the result of substitution to perform this $shift\ 0\ (-1)$ on. However, in wnf_1 what we really wanted is $wnf_1 (beta\ b\ a')$, and we can rewrite it a bit:

$$\begin{aligned} wnf_1 (beta\ b\ a') &= wnf_1 (shift\ 0\ (-1)\ (subst\ b\ 0\ (shift\ 0\ 1\ a'))) \\ &= shift\ 0\ (-1)\ (wnf_1 (subst\ b\ 0\ (shift\ 0\ 1\ a'))) \end{aligned}$$

The first equality is just the definition of $beta$ and the second equality is because removing the variable 0 that is substituted away before or after weak normalisation gives the same result. This observation then allows us to translate wnf_1 to wnf_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} wnf_2 &:: Tm \rightarrow Subst_2 \rightarrow Val_2 \\ wnf_2 (Abs\ b)\ sub &= Closure_2\ b\ sub \\ wnf_2 (Var\ n)\ sub &= sub\ !!\ n \end{aligned}$$

```

511   wnf2 (App f a) sub =
512     let f' = wnf2 f sub; ~a' = wnf2 a sub
513     in case f' of Closure2 b sub' → shift0Val (-1) (wnf2 b (shift0List 1 (a' : sub')))
514         Spine2 v as → Spine2 v (a' : as)
515

```

516 Reifying values to normal forms works the same as *reify₁*, except that for the case of a
517 λ -abstraction *Closure₂ t sub*, the new substitution for the function body *b* should now be
518 *Spine₂ 0 [] : shift0List 1 sub*, where *Spine₂ 0 []* means that the bound variable 0 of the
519 function body *b* is still 0 itself, applied to no arguments. And *shift0List 1* is applied to *sub*
520 because *sub* is a substitution applied to *Abs b* rather than *b*.

```

522   reify2 :: Val2 → Tm
523   reify2 (Closure2 b sub) = Abs (reify2 (wnf2 b (Spine2 0 [] : shift0List 1 sub)))
524   reify2 (Spine2 v as) = foldr (λ r → r · reify2 a) (Var v) as
525

```

526 Putting things together, we have our new normaliser:

```

527   nf2 :: Tm → Tm
528   nf2 t = let n = fv t in reify2 (wnf2 t (reflect2 n))
529   reflect2 :: Int → Subst2
530   reflect2 n = map (λ v → Spine2 v []) [0..n]
531

```

532 The function *reflect₂* creates the trivial substitution for the free variables of the term *t*,
533 substituting each free variable *v* for *v* itself. (Side remark: *reflect₂* is rather trivial here, but
534 if we do normalisation for typed languages with η -equalities, this *reflect* function would be
535 more interesting.)

538 8 Defunctional normalisation by evaluation

539 Now let us move on to optimise *wnf₂* further. A notable source of inefficiency is the work
540 that we need to do for shifting de Bruijn indices. De Bruijn indices are only for representing
541 variables in a scope-safe way. They shall not be a computational bottleneck in normalisation.
542 Therefore we would like to optimise them out.

543 Let us first work on the shifting in this line of *wnf₂*:

```

544   Closure2 b sub' → shift0Val (-1) (wnf2 b (shift0List 1 (a' : sub')))
545

```

546 These two shifting operations have their origin from substitution, namely the following line
547 from our earlier *wnf₁* (with *beta* inlined for easier comparison):

```

548   Abs b → wnf1 (shift 0 (-1) (subst b 0 (shift 0 1 a')))
549

```

550 An observation useful to us is that in the setting of *wnf₂* the lazy substitution *a' : sub'* substitutes
551 all the free variables of *b*. Because weak normalisation on a term never introduces new free
552 variables, we know for sure that the free variables in the term *wnf₂ b (shift0List 1 (a' : sub'))*
553 must all come from free variables in the lazy substitution *a' : sub'*. Therefore we could do the
554 final step *shift0Val (-1)* of shifting free variables by -1 before the *wnf₂* as well. That is to
555 say, we have equality

```

556   shift0Val (-1) (wnf2 b (shift0List 1 (a' : sub')))
557   = wnf2 b (shift0List (-1) (shift0List 1 (a' : sub')))
558

```

559
560
561

562 Then $\text{shift0List } (-1)$ ($\text{shift0List } 1\dots$) just cancels out!

$$\begin{aligned} 563 & \quad \text{wnf}_2 b (\text{shift0List } (-1) (\text{shift0List } 1 (a' : \text{sub}')))) \\ 564 & \quad = \text{wnf}_2 b (a' : \text{sub}') \end{aligned}$$

566 The observation allows us to optimise wnf_2 into the following wnf_3 , resulting in a new
567 normaliser nf_3 :
568

$$\begin{aligned} 569 & \quad \text{wnf}_3 :: \text{Tm} \rightarrow \text{Subst}_2 \rightarrow \text{Val}_2 \\ 570 & \quad \text{wnf}_3 (\text{Var } n) \text{ sub} = \text{sub} !! n \\ 571 & \quad \text{wnf}_3 (\text{Abs } b) \text{ sub} = \text{Closure}_2 b \text{ sub} \\ 572 & \quad \text{wnf}_3 (\text{App } f a) \text{ sub} = \mathbf{let} f' = \text{wnf}_3 f \text{ sub}; \sim a' = \text{wnf}_3 a \text{ sub} \\ 573 & \quad \quad \quad \mathbf{in case } f' \mathbf{ of } \text{Closure}_2 b \text{ sub}' \rightarrow \text{wnf}_3 b (a' : \text{sub}') \\ 574 & \quad \quad \quad \text{Spine}_2 v \text{ as} \rightarrow \text{Spine}_2 v (a' : \text{as}) \\ 575 & \quad \quad \quad \text{nf}_3 :: \text{Tm} \rightarrow \text{Tm} \\ 576 & \quad \quad \quad \text{nf}_3 t = \mathbf{let} n = \text{fv } t \mathbf{ in } \text{reify}_2 (\text{wnf}_3 t (\text{reflect}_2 n)) \end{aligned}$$

579 The normaliser nf_3 is essentially already *normalisation by evaluation* for untyped lambda
580 calculus. To normalise a term t , we first evaluate it into a semantic domain $\text{Subst}_2 \rightarrow \text{Val}_2$.
581 Note the semantic domain is $\text{Subst}_2 \rightarrow \text{Val}_2$ rather than just Val_2 ! From the resulting value,
582 we obtain a normal form by reflecting the context of the term t into a substitution and then
583 reifying the value.
584

585 9 Functional normalisation by evaluation

586 I have been saying that $\text{wnf}_3 t$ *evaluates* a term into a semantic domain. However, if we
587 are pedantic with terminology, we should only use the word ‘evaluate’ if wnf_3 computes
588 compositionally (i.e. wnf_3 should be a fold of terms). Unfortunately, wnf_3 is not (at least not
589 on the nose) compositional because of this line:
590

$$591 \quad \text{Closure}_2 b \text{ sub}' \rightarrow \text{wnf}_3 b (a' : \text{sub}')$$

593 where we do recursion on b but b is not a subterm of the input $\text{App } f a$.

594 However, if we look more closely at wnf_3 , we see that the source of the problem is that
595 when wnf_3 sees a λ -abstraction, we simply stored the function body b and the lazy substitution
596 sub as $\text{Closure}_2 b \text{ sub}$ without doing structural recursion into the subterm b . Later, when
597 wnf_3 uses $\text{Closure}_2 b \text{ sub}$, it is used for a recursion $\text{wnf}_3 b (a' : \text{sub}')$ into the function body b
598 (with an extended substitution). Therefore the computation of wnf_3 is in fact compositional –
599 we just need to refactor wnf_3 a bit to make $\text{wnf}_3 (\text{Abs } b) \text{ sub}$ a function $\lambda a \rightarrow \text{wnf}_3 b (a : \text{sub})$
600 of type $\text{Val}_2 \rightarrow \text{Val}_2$ that performs structural recursion into the subterm b . Correspondingly,
601 where we previously do $\text{Closure}_2 b \text{ sub}' \rightarrow \text{wnf}_3 b (a' : \text{sub}')$, we now no longer need to do
602 the recursion $\text{wnf}_3 b$ here, as this job has been done by $\text{wnf}_3 (\text{Abs } b) \text{ sub}$ now.
603

604 Turning the constructor $\text{Closure}_2 \text{ Tm } \text{Subst}_2$ into a genuine function $\text{Val}_2 \rightarrow \text{Val}_2$ is the
605 key idea, but there is one more small change that we also need to make. Another place that
606 Closure_2 is involved is when it is reified:
607

$$608 \quad \text{reify}_2 (\text{Closure}_2 b \text{ sub}) = \text{Abs} (\text{reify}_2 (\text{wnf}_2 b (\text{Spine}_2 0 [] : \text{shift0List } 1 \text{ sub})))$$

610 where the free variables in the original substitution sub are shifted by 1. After refactoring
611 $\text{Closure}_2 b \text{ sub}$ into a function $\text{Val}_2 \rightarrow \text{Val}_2$, we will no longer have direct access to sub to do
612

613 *shift0List* 1 *sub*. But this problem is easy to fix: we can just make the function $Val_2 \rightarrow Val_2$
 614 take an additional integer argument and apply it to *sub*.

615 Now let us execute this refactoring. Firstly, we need to change the constructor *Closure*₂
 616 from storing a function body and a lazy substitution to a genuine function:

```
617
618   data Val4 = Closure4 (Int → Val4 → Val4) | Spine4 Int (LazyList Val4)
619   type Subst4 = LazyList Val4
620   wnf4 :: Tm → Subst4 → Val4
621   wnf4 (Var n) sub = sub !! n
622
```

623 And when *wnf*₄ sees a λ -abstraction, it defines a function that structurally recurs into *b*:

```
624   wnf4 (Abs b) sub = Closure4 ( $\lambda i$  ( $\sim a$ ) → wnf4 b (a : shift0List4 i sub))
625
```

626 Correspondingly, in the case of *App* *f* *a*, we just need to call the function in the place where
 627 we previously had *Closure*₂ *b* *sub'* → *wnf*₃ *b* (*a'* : *sub'*):

```
628   wnf4 (App f a) sub = let f' = wnf4 f sub;  $\sim a'$  = wnf4 a sub
629                       in case f' of Closure4 b → b 0 a'
630                       Spine4 v as → Spine4 v (a' : as)
631
```

632 And in reification, where we previously did

```
633   reify2 (Closure2 b sub) = Abs (reify2 (wnf2 b (Spine2 0 [] : shift0List 1 sub)))
634
```

635 now we just need to do:

```
636   reify4 :: Val4 → Tm
637   reify4 (Closure4 b) = Abs $ reify4 (b 1 (Spine4 0 []))
638   reify4 (Spine4 v as) = foldr ( $\lambda a r \rightarrow r \cdot reify_4 a$ ) (Var v) as
639
```

640 Shifting on closures needs some slight refactoring as well:

```
641   shift0Val4 :: Int → Val4 → Val4
642   shift0Val4 0 v = v
643   shift0Val4 i (Spine4 n as) = Spine4 (n + i) (shift0List4 i as)
644   shift0Val4 i (Closure4 b) = Closure4 (b ∘ (+i))
645   shift0List4 :: Int → Subst4 → Subst4
646   shift0List4 0 vs = vs
647   shift0List4 i vs = map (shift0Val4 i) vs
648
```

649 Reflection however stays the same:

```
650   reflect4 :: Int → Subst4
651   reflect4 n = map ( $\lambda v \rightarrow Spine_4 v []$ ) [0..n]
652
```

653 And our new normaliser is again:

```
654   nf4 :: Tm → Tm
655   nf4 t = let n = fv t in reify4 (wnf4 t (reflect4 n))
656
```

657 After performing this refactoring, *wnf*₄ becomes compositional – it is a fold on the syntax
 658 of lambda terms. I would like to emphasise that we have *wnf*₄ only for making the hidden
 659 compositional nature *wnf*₃ explicit. In terms of performance, *wnf*₄ makes no improvement
 660
 661
 662
 663

664 over wnf_3 . They do normalisation in exactly the same way. In fact, wnf_3 is preferred in practice
 665 because it does not need the host language to support higher-order functions, while wnf_4 does.
 666 In the literature, the way that wnf_3 deals with λ -abstractions is called *defunctionalization*
 667 (Danvy and Nielsen 2001): it implements (higher-order) functions as first-order data (a syntax
 668 tree paired with the lazy substitution).

669 The normaliser nf_4 is a milestone of this article: it is essentially what you would get if
 670 you extract the algorithmic content of a categorical-glueing normalisation proof for typed
 671 calculi (Fiore 2022, p. 28) and erase all the type information. The functions $shift0Val_4$ and
 672 $shift0List_4$ correspond to the presheaf actions in the normalisation proof, and the integer
 673 arguments of those shifting functions correspond to the weakening substitutions in the proof.

674 The only major difference between nf_4 and the algorithmic content of a normalisation
 675 proof is that nf_4 only computes β -normal forms while normalisation proofs of typed calculi
 676 typically also do normalisation of η -equalities for (dependent) functions and pairs. However,
 677 this is not because we did anything wrong – this is just because normalising eta-equalities is
 678 *type directed* while here we are in the setting of an untyped language, which does not give us
 679 any information telling us which variables should be η -expanded (this is the reason why our
 680 reflection functions look so trivial).
 681
 682

683 10 Normalisation by evaluation with de Bruijn levels

684 Let us continue our optimisation journey. The NbE normaliser nf_3 (and nf_4) still has one
 685 shifting operation: when reifying a closure we had:

$$686 \text{reify}_2 (\text{Closure}_2 b \text{ sub}) = \text{Abs} (\text{reify}_2 (wnf_2 b (\text{Spine}_2 0 [] : \text{shift0List } 1 \text{ sub})))$$

687
 688
 689
 690
 691 The shifting operation is not cheap: it needs to traverse the whole substitution to increment
 692 all de Bruijn indices by 1. How can we make this faster? Lazy tagging! Well lazy tagging
 693 will do the job (and we will do it later), but there is in fact an extremely simple trick that
 694 would work here too.

695 At the moment, variables are represented as de Bruijn indices, and to bring a de Bruijn
 696 index v from a context of n variables to a context of $n + 1$ variables, we need to shift v to
 697 $v + 1$ (an $O(1)$ operation). Can we find another representation of variables so that shifting a
 698 variable from a context of n variables to a context of $n + 1$ variables is even better than $O(1)$?
 699

700 The answer is yes! We represent a variable by an integer just like de Bruijn indices, but
 701 count from outside in rather than inside out. For example, in the context of b in the term
 702 $\lambda x. \lambda y. \lambda z. b$, assuming b has no free variables other than x, y, z , we will represent x as 0, y
 703 as 1, and z as 2. In comparison, de Bruijn indices would represent z as 0, y as 1, and x as 2. In
 704 this way, if b is a λ -abstraction, $b = \lambda w. c$, in the context of c , the variables x, y , and z would
 705 still be 0, 1, and 2. Shifting variables into the next level is $O(0)$ (i.e. a no-op)! This kind of
 706 variable representation is sometimes called de Bruijn *levels*.
 707

708 Using this idea, we can optimise nf_3 by using de Bruijn levels (instead of de Bruijn indices)
 709 in our semantic domain. The input terms can still use de Bruijn indices as before, and we do
 710 not need to transform them into de Bruijn levels. Note that this optimisation is only possible
 711 because in the process of weak normalisation (wnf_2 , wnf_3 , and wnf_4), we always (weakly)
 712 normalise a function body when it receives its concrete argument. Therefore all variables are
 713 instantiated *from outside to inside*.
 714

For this optimisation, we do not need to change wnf_3 , as integer representations of variables are only dealt in the $reify$ and $reflect$ functions. We change $reify_2 :: Val_2 \rightarrow Tm$ to

$$reify_5 :: Int \rightarrow Val_2 \rightarrow Tm$$

$$reify_5 \text{ lvl } (Closure_2 \text{ b sub}) = Abs (reify_5 (lvl + 1) (wnf_3 \text{ b } (Spine_2 \text{ lvl } [] : sub)))$$

Here when we reify a function body, we (lazily) substitute the current de Bruijn level lvl for the newly bound variable, instead of the de Bruijn index 0 as we did previously in $reify_2$. This necessitates us to know the current level of the input value, so $reify_5$ now has an additional Int argument lvl . Because of this representation, we do not need to do $shift0List \ 1$ to sub anymore.

Conversely, when we reify a spine back to a normal form, the output has type Tm , which still uses de Bruijn indices. Hence we need to convert a de Bruijn level v back to a de Bruijn index $lvl - v - 1$:

$$reify_5 \text{ lvl } (Spine_2 \text{ v as}) = foldr (\lambda s \rightarrow s \cdot reify_5 \text{ lvl } a) (Var (lvl - v - 1)) \text{ as}$$

Similarly, the $reflect$ function should be refactored to use de Bruijn levels as well. Therefore we change $reflect_2 \text{ n} = map (\lambda v \rightarrow Spine_2 \text{ v } []) [0..n]$ to

$$reflect_5 :: Int \rightarrow Subst_2$$

$$reflect_5 \text{ n} = map (\lambda v \rightarrow Spine_2 (n - v) []) [0..n]$$

We do not need to change wnf_3 at all. Therefore our new normaliser is

$$nf_5 :: Tm \rightarrow Tm$$

$$nf_5 \text{ t} = \mathbf{let} \text{ n} = fv \text{ t} \mathbf{in} \text{ reify}_5 (n + 1) (wnf_3 \text{ t } (reflect_5 \text{ n}))$$

The normaliser nf_5 is exactly the efficient version of NbE for untyped lambda calculus that you would find in the literature, such as in András Kovács's elaboration zoo (Kovács 2020) or Abel (2013, §3.1, 3.2). This is an efficient normaliser of untyped lambda calculus and we have reconstructed it by a series of optimisations from the naive applicative-order normaliser.

11 Reflection on NbE

Now is a good time to reflect on what we have done from the very beginning:

1. *We made the normalisation of arguments lazy.* Our rationale for this is that if the argument does not get used in the function body at all, we do not waste any time on normalising the argument.
2. *We switched our evaluation strategy from applicative order to what may be called weak applicative order.* This strategy can be summarised as *no β -reductions are allowed under the scope of a λ -abstraction, unless the lambda abstraction has no arguments*, or alternatively, *normalising a term to a weak normal form first before normalising under lambda abstractions*. Our rationale for this is that if we delay normalising a function body b until the bound variable x receives its concrete value a , we can skip normalisation of arguments M that are supplied to x but are actually not used by a when x becomes a .
3. *We used the trick of lazy tagging to implement substitutions* to make substitutions fast.
4. *We optimised out shifting de Bruijn indices by some algebraic simplification and using de Bruijn levels in weak normal forms.*

Now I would say that we understand normalisation by evaluation better:

766 *Normalisation by evaluation is weak-applicative-order normalisation with*
 767 *meta-level laziness, lazy substitution, and de Bruijn levels.*

768 Also, the version of NbE extracted from categorical glueing proofs is only weak-applicative-
 769 order normalisation with lazy substitution.
 770

771 12 Adversarial Exploit of NbE

772 We shall not stop at NbE. With our knowledge gained in the reconstruction of NbE, let us push
 773 NbE further. Recall that the reason that led to using weak-applicative-order normalisation is
 774 that when we normalise $App\ f\ a$, the optimal thing to do for the function f is to normalise it
 775 just enough to expose its outermost λ -abstraction. However, for the argument a we chose to
 776 also normalise it to expose the outermost λ -abstraction because the argument a may be used
 777 as a function in the body of f . Our strategy for f is good, but our strategy for a is based on the
 778 assumption that a will be used as a function inside f later.
 779

780 Of course this assumption does not always hold. For an extreme example, we can have a
 781 term (with a free variable x)
 782

$$783 \quad (\lambda y. x\ y\ y\ y\ y\ y\ \dots\ y)\ (expensiveTm\ 100)$$

784 where the argument $expensiveTm\ 100$ is used as arguments in the function body 1000000
 785 times. NbE would be very slow on this term because the term $expensiveTm\ 100$ would be
 786 normalised to weak normal forms before (lazy) substitution, and then in the function body
 787 it would be duplicated 1000000 times, and the NbE would reify the weak normal form of
 788 $expensiveTm\ 100$ 1000000 times, one time for each occurrence of y .
 789

790 $nbeAdversarialExploit :: Tm$

791 $nbeAdversarialExploit =$

792 $Abs\ (foldr\ (\lambda_ r \rightarrow r \cdot Var\ 0)\ (Var\ 1)\ [1..1000000]) \cdot expensiveTm\ 100$
 793

794 Our naive normaliser nf_0 takes a few seconds to normalise this term on my computer:
 795

796 $\gg\>\> fv\ (nf_0\ nbeAdversarialExploit)$

797 \emptyset

798 But our best NbE normaliser nf_5 takes a much longer time.
 799

800 Let us fix this problem in the rest of this article. Our plan is that when we normalise
 801 $App\ f\ a$, we create a lazy thunk of the full normal form of a and pass it to the function body
 802 of f . Later when we reify a value and see a thunk of a full normal form in a spine, we can just
 803 force this thunk. In this way, if the argument a is used in the function body f many times as
 804 arguments in a spine, they would share the same thunk of the full normal form.
 805

806 The plan is simple, but a technical difficulty is that when we weakly normalise $App\ f\ a$ and
 807 create the thunk of the full normal form a' of a , the de Bruijn level where a' is created will
 808 be different from the de Bruijn level where a' will be used inside the function body f . This
 809 highlights the *disadvantage* of de Bruijn levels over de Bruijn indices: a closed term with de
 810 Bruijn indices is stable if we move this term to some other locations, while a closed term
 811 with de Bruijn levels is not stable. For example, consider the following term in the context of
 812 one free variable x :
 813

$$814 \quad (\lambda z. x\ (\lambda w. z))\ (\lambda y. y\ y)$$

817 Using de Bruijn levels, the free variable x is represented by 0, and y is represented by 1.
 818 However, if we substitute $\lambda . y y$ for z , we obtain $x (\lambda . (\lambda . y y))$, where y should be
 819 shifted to 2 (because w is 1).

820 To fix this problem, we shall revert to using de Bruijn indices instead of de Bruijn levels.
 821 Recall that previously we switched from de Bruijn indices to levels when optimising nf_3 to
 822 nf_5 to save the time of shifting de Bruijn indices. But we mentioned that we had another
 823 solution to do this: lazy tagging. Therefore let us first do another optimised version of nf_3
 824 using lazy shifting of de Bruijn indices.
 825

826 13 NbE with lazy shifting of de Bruijn indices

827
 828 Very similar to the example of *Tree'* that we used earlier to demonstrate lazy tagging on trees,
 829 we will need lists storing lazy tags that represent shift offsets that are logically applied to the
 830 de Bruijn indices. For this we define a type *SList a* of lists with lazy tags of shift indices. We
 831 will use this type to replace *LazyList a* that we used before to represent lazy substitutions.
 832

833 **data** *SList a* = *Nil* | *Cons_ Int ~a (SList a)*

834 The type of values (weak normal forms with lazy substitutions) is the same as before, except
 835 that we now use *SList*:
 836

837 **data** *Val₆* = *Closure₆ Tm Subst₆* | *Spine₆ Int (SList Val₆)*
 838 **type** *Subst₆* = *SList Val₆*

839
 840 We will have more than one type that supports index shifting, so this time let us define a
 841 typeclass with a single member function *shift0 i v* that shifts all de Bruijn indices in v by i .
 842 We will not need the general case *shift x i v* of shifting with a cut-off parameter x .
 843

844 **class** *Shift0 a where shift0 :: Int → a → a*

845 Shifting a list with lazy tags only remembers the offset i lazily without actually performing
 846 the shifting operations. It is clearly $O(1)$. In contrast, previously in *shift0List* we needed to
 847 map over the list to shift every element.
 848

849 **instance** *Shift0 a ⇒ Shift0 (SList a) where*
 850 *shift0 :: Shift0 a ⇒ Int → SList a → SList a*
 851 *shift0 i Nil = Nil*
 852 *shift0 i (Cons_ j v vs) = Cons_ (i + j) v vs*

853 Shifting a value is easy too. For a closure, we use *shift0* for *SList* to shift the lazy substitution.
 854 For a spine, we shift the variable immediately and use *shift0* for *SList* to shift the arguments.
 855

856
 857 **instance** *Shift0 Val₆ where*
 858 *shift0 :: Int → Val₆ → Val₆*
 859 *shift0 i (Closure₆ b sub) = Closure₆ b (shift0 i sub)*
 860 *shift0 i (Spine₆ j as) = Spine₆ (i + j) (shift0 i as)*

861
 862 To make our life later easier, this time let us use pattern synonyms of Haskell to make lazy
 863 tagging transparent. The type *Listview a* is the functor that captures the shape of a list (with
 864 lazy payloads but strict structure).
 865

866 **data** *Listview a x* = *NilView* | *ConsView ~a x*
 867

A *SList* a is logically a list of a viewed from the following function, where we push the lazy tag down (c.f. the *push* function in the earlier example of lazy tagging for binary trees):

```

viewSList :: Shift0 a => SList a -> ListView a (SList a)
viewSList Nil = NilView
viewSList (Cons_ i v vs) | i ≠ 0    = ConsView (shift0 i v) (shift0 i vs)
                             | otherwise = ConsView v vs

```

We define a pattern synonym *Cons* v vs : when we use the pattern *Cons* v vs to match again an element $as :: SList a$, it will automatically applies *viewSList* to as . And when we use *Cons* v vs to construct an element of type *SList* a , the lazy tag is going to be set to 0. Using this pattern, the user interface of *SList* will be exactly the same as an ordinary list.

```

pattern Cons v vs ← (viewSList → ConsView v vs) where
  Cons ~v vs = Cons_ 0 v vs

```

We will need some standard list-processing functions for *SList*. They are straightforward:

```

lookupSL :: Shift0 a => SList a -> Int -> a
lookupSL Nil _ = error "index out of range"
lookupSL (Cons v vs) i = if i ≡ 0 then v else lookupSL vs (i - 1)

foldrSL :: Shift0 a => (a -> r -> r) -> r -> SList a -> r
foldrSL f r Nil = r
foldrSL f r (Cons v vs) = f v (foldrSL f r vs)

dropSL :: Shift0 a => Int -> SList a -> SList a
dropSL 0 as = as
dropSL i Nil = Nil
dropSL i (Cons _ as) = dropSL (i - 1) as

```

Our new weak normaliser is the same as wnf_3 except that it uses the new Val_6 for values:

```

wnf6 :: Tm -> Subst6 -> Val6
wnf6 (Var n) sub = lookupSL sub n
wnf6 (Abs b) sub = Closure6 b sub
wnf6 (App f a) sub = let f' = wnf6 f sub; ~a' = wnf6 a sub
                    in case f' of Closure6 b sub' -> wnf6 b (Cons a' sub')
                    Spine6 v as -> Spine6 v (Cons a' as)

```

Similarly, $reify_6$ is the same as $reify_2$ except it uses the new data type Val_6 :

```

reify6 :: Val6 -> Tm
reify6 (Closure6 t sub) = Abs (reify6 (wnf6 t (Cons (Spine6 0 Nil) (shift0 1 sub))))
reify6 (Spine6 v as) = foldrSL (λ r -> r · reify6 a) (Var v) as

```

The function $reflect_6$ is the same as $reflect_2$:

```

reflect6 :: Int -> Subst6
reflect6 n = foldr (λ x rs -> Cons (Spine6 x Nil) rs) Nil [0..n]

```

These give us the new normaliser nf_6 , which is defunctional NbE with de Bruijn indices (rather than levels). Because of lazy tagging, the shift operations have $O(1)$ complexity, so

919 this version has the same asymptotic complexity as nf_5 (the version using de Bruijn levels)
 920 on all input, but of course the constant factor of nf_6 is slightly bigger than that of nf_5 .

921 $nf_6 :: Tm \rightarrow Tm$
 922
 923 $nf_6 t = \mathbf{let} n = fv\ t \mathbf{ in} reify_6 (wnf_6\ t\ (reflect_6\ n))$

924 14 NbE with shared normal forms

925 Now we have the needed infrastructure to implement our idea of improving NbE by creating a
 926 thunk of a normal form for a function argument a in the case of weakly normalising $App\ f\ a$.
 927 This thunk will be used like a *cache*: later if the function argument a is duplicated in different
 928 places in the function body, full normalisation of a will use the same thunk of a .
 929

930 To do this, we change the type of Val_6 to have an additional constructor $Cached_7\ t\ v$, where
 931 t is (a thunk of) the normal form of the value v . We shall have the invariant that $Cached$ is
 932 never nested, i.e. $Cached\ _ (Cached\ _ _)$ is not allowed.
 933

934 **data** $Val_7 = Closure_7\ Tm\ Subst_7 \mid Spine_7\ Int\ (SList\ Val_7) \mid Cached_7\ \sim Tm_S\ Val_7$
 935 **type** $Subst_7 = SList\ Val_7$
 936

937 Up to now, we have used the type Tm of terms to store normal forms, but this time we are
 938 going to put normal forms in lazy substitutions so we need a new version of Tm that supports
 939 lazy shifting. To do this, we modify the constructors Abs and App of Tm to store an additional
 940 integer lazy tag (an integer i means that $shift0\ i$ has been logically applied to this term):
 941

942 **data** $Tm_S = Abs_S\ Int\ Tm_S \mid App_S\ Int\ Tm_S\ Tm_S \mid Var_S\ Int$
 943

944 Shifting is again $O(1)$ because we just need to accumulate it in the lazy tags:

945 **instance** $Shift_0\ Tm_S$ **where**
 946 $shift0\ i\ (Abs_S\ j\ b) = Abs_S\ (i + j)\ b$
 947 $shift0\ i\ (App_S\ j\ f\ a) = App_S\ (i + j)\ f\ a$
 948 $shift0\ i\ (Var_S\ j) = Var_S\ (i + j)$
 949

950 Similarly, shifting a value is $O(1)$ because $shift0$ for $SList\ a$ and Tm_S is $O(1)$ and there are no
 951 two consecutive layers of $Cached$:
 952

953 **instance** $Shift_0\ Val_7$ **where**
 954 $shift0\ i\ (Closure_7\ b\ sub) = Closure_7\ b\ (shift0\ i\ sub)$
 955 $shift0\ i\ (Spine_7\ j\ as) = Spine_7\ (i + j)\ (shift0\ i\ as)$
 956 $shift0\ i\ (Cached_7\ n\ v) = Cached_7\ (shift0\ i\ n)\ (shift0\ i\ v)$
 957

958 Let us define two auxiliary functions for ignoring and preparing cached normal forms:

959 $ignoreCache :: Val_7 \rightarrow Val_7$ $makeCache :: Val_7 \rightarrow Val_7$
 960 $ignoreCache\ (Cached_7\ _ v) = v$ $makeCache\ v@(Cached_7\ _ _) = v$
 961 $ignoreCache\ v = v$ $makeCache\ v = Cached_7\ (reify_7\ v)\ v$
 962

963 Our new weak normaliser now makes cached normal forms for function arguments (and
 964 ignores the cached normal forms for functions):

965 $wnf_7 :: Tm \rightarrow Subst_7 \rightarrow Val_7$
 966 $wnf_7\ (Var\ n)\ sub = lookup_{SL}\ sub\ n$
 967 $wnf_7\ (Abs\ b)\ sub = Closure_7\ b\ sub$
 968
 969

```

970      wnf7 (App f a) sub =
971          let f' = wnf7 f sub
972              ~a' = makeCache (wnf7 a sub)
973          in case ignoreCache f' of
974              Closure7 b sub' → wnf7 b (Cons a' sub')
975              Spine7 v as → Spine7 v (Cons a' as)

```

When we reify a value, we can use a cached normal form when there is one, otherwise everything stays the same as *reify*₆:

```

980      reify7 :: Val7 → TmS
981      reify7 (Closure7 t sub) = AbsS 0 (reify7 (wnf7 t (Cons (Spine7 0 Nil) (shift 0 1 sub))))
982      reify7 (Spine7 v as) = foldrSL (λx r → AppS 0 r (reify7 x)) (VarS v) as
983      reify7 (Cached7 c _) = c

```

Reflection does not change at all:

```

987      reflect7 :: Int → SList Val7
988      reflect7 n = foldr (λx rs → Cons (Spine7 x Nil) rs) Nil [0..n]

```

With these ingredients, our new normaliser is again *reify*₇ (wnf₇ t (reflect₇ n)). Wait! Now *reify*₇ produces an element of *Tm*_S, a normal form containing lazy shifts, and of course what we really want is a normal form of type *Tm*, without any lazy shifts. Therefore we need a function *forceShifts* :: *Tm*_S → *Tm* triggers the lazy shifts stored in the resulting normal form (of type *Tm*_S) and produces a normal form (of type *Tm*) that does not have lazy shifts.

This function does not sound hard, does it? It turns out this function is a bit tricky to get efficient. We do not want this *forceShifts* function to be more expensive than the actual normalisation process itself, so the naive implementation below is not good enough:

```

1000     forceShiftsSpec :: TmS → Tm
1001     forceShiftsSpec (VarS v) = Var v
1002     forceShiftsSpec (AbsS i b) = shift 0 i (Abs (forceShiftsSpec b))
1003     forceShiftsSpec (AppS i f a) = shift 0 i (App (forceShiftsSpec f) (forceShiftsSpec a))

```

The difficulty here is that we cannot reduce the composition of two shifting operations into a single one. We do have *shift* 0 *i* ∘ *shift* 0 *j* = *shift* 0 (*i* + *j*), but unfortunately for the case of *Abs*_S *i* *b* above, we have a λ-abstraction, and *shift* 0 *i* (*Abs* *b*) becomes *Abs* (*shift* 1 *i* *b*). In general, the composition of two shifts is not equal to a single shift:

```

1010      shift x i ∘ shift y j ≠ shift _ _

```

To understand shifting functions better, we represent any function *S* : *Int* → *Int* transforming de Bruijn indices as a sequence *ss* = [*s*₀, *s*₁, ..., *s*_N], which encodes the information that the variable of de Bruijn index 0 should be transformed to *s*0, the variable of de Bruijn index 1 should be transformed to *s*₁, etc. Therefore the function *S* is just *S* *v* = *ss* ! *v*. Then the crucial observation is that the composition *S* ∘ *shift* 0 *i* is

```

1019      (S ∘ shift 0 i) v = S (v + i) = ss ! (v + i) = (drop i ss) ! v

```

1021 That is to say, the composite function $S \circ \text{shift } 0 \ i$ can be represented by the sequence $\text{drop } i \ ss$.
 1022 Similarly, when we descend from the context of $\text{Abs } b$ to the context of b , the sequence that
 1023 represents the function S changes from ss to $0 : \text{map } (1+) \ ss$.

1024 Therefore to maintain a compact representation of composites of shifting functions, we
 1025 need a functional data structure for a sequence of integers with the following operations:

- 1026 (1) pushing a 0 to the head of the sequence,
- 1027 (2) adding 1 to all the integers in the sequence,
- 1028 (3) dropping the first i elements of the sequence for any given integer i ,
- 1029 (4) accessing the i -th element for any given integer i .

1030 We want the data structure to be persistent because, for $\text{App } f \ a$, the computation forks into
 1031 two branches for f and a respectively, and modifying the sequence in one branch shall not
 1032 affect the computation in other branches. We may call this interface ‘stack with *bulk pop*’.
 1033 Our lazy tagging list SList Int supports the first two operations in $O(1)$ and the other two
 1034 operations in $O(i)$. The version of forceShifts with SList Int is then as follows.
 1035

```

1037   instance Shift0 Int where shift0 i j = i + j
1038   forceShifts :: SList Int → TmS → Tm
1039   forceShifts ss (VarS v) = Var (lookupSL ss v)
1040   forceShifts ss (AbsS i b) = let ss' = Cons 0 (shift0 1 (dropSL i ss))
1041                               in Abs (forceShifts ss' b)
1042   forceShifts ss (AppS i f a) = let ss' = dropSL i ss
1043                               in App (forceShifts ss' f) (forceShifts ss' a)
1044
1045
  
```

1046 This gives us the new normaliser, normalisation by evaluation with shared normal forms:

```

1047   nf7 :: Tm → Tm
1048   nf7 t = let n = fv t; ss = foldr (λv rs → Cons v rs) Nil [0..n]
1049           in forceShifts ss (reify7 (wnf7 t (reflect7 n)))
1050
  
```

1051 Indeed, nf_7 is much faster on the $\text{nbeAdversarialExploit}$ program than nf_5 was slow.

1052 Unfortunately, our SList Int is too slow for dropping the first i elements. A better
 1053 implementation of stack with bulk pop would be using balanced trees that support log-
 1054 time splitting, such as finger trees or red-black trees, which will give us an $O(\log i)$ -time
 1055 implementation of dropping i elements. In our concrete application, i is bound by the *depth*
 1056 of λ -abstractions, so i will not be too big in practice.
 1057

1058 However, if we want a version of nf_7 that has better or equal asymptotic complexity than
 1059 NbE on all families of input programs, a logarithmic factor is not good enough either. We
 1060 need pushing, bulk popping, and adding all to be $O(1)$; accessing can be in $O(i)$ time is fine
 1061 because for NbE we also did linear lookup for variables. A fully persistent data structure
 1062 in the literature that supports all these operations in $O(1)$ is the one by [Alstrup and Holm](#)
 1063 (2000). However, this is a rather complex data structure so we will not implement it here.
 1064

1065 15 Stateful Shifts Forcing

1067 If we look at forceShifts again, we see that we use the sequence in a very predictable manner:

```

1068   forceShifts ss (AppS i f a) = let ss' = dropSL i ss
1069                               in App (forceShifts ss' f) (forceShifts ss' a)
1070
  
```

1071

1072 We first drop the first i elements of the sequence ss , and then we do recursion for f and
 1073 a . Both computations $forceShifts\ ss'\ f$ and $forceShifts\ ss'\ a$ may subsequently modify the
 1074 sequence, which is the reason why I said we wanted a persistent implementation of the
 1075 sequence. However, we *can* implement $forceShifts$ with a mutable sequence, as long as we
 1076 make the two recursion calls *sequential* and ensure that $forceShifts$ restores the sequence
 1077 after it finishes its computation. Doing this will imply that we give up the possibility of
 1078 parallelising $forceShifts$, but this is an acceptable cost.

1080 With mutation, stacks with bulk pops can easily be implemented as a mutable array, for
 1081 which we remember an integer $delta$ that is logically added to all integers stored in the array
 1082 and an integer end that is logically the top of the stack:

```
1083     data IndicesArr s = IndicesArr { delta :: Int, end :: Int, arr :: STUArray s Int Int }
1084
```

1085 For mutable arrays we will use Haskell's $STUArray$, whose operations are encapsulated in the
 1086 ST monad for a pure interface. Most of our subsequent functions will be in a reader monad
 1087 transformer providing an $IndicesArr$, applied to the ST monad:

```
1088
1089     type M s a = IndicesArr s → ST s a
1090
```

1091 To access the v -th element from the top of the stack, we just read the array (which is $O(1)$).
 1092 We also need to remember to add $delta$ to the result, since $delta$ is logically added to all
 1093 integers stored in the stack:

```
1094     lookupIA :: Int → M s Tm
1095     lookupIA v IndicesArr { .. } = do i ← readArray arr (end - v - 1)
1096                                     return (Var (delta + i))
1097
```

1098 Adding an integer to the stack just adds to the lazy $delta$:

```
1100     addIA :: Int → M s a → M s a
1101     addIA i m ia@IndicesArr { .. } = m ia { delta = delta + i }
1102
```

1103 Similarly, dropping i elements just moves the end cursor:

```
1104
1105     dropIA :: Int → M s a → M s a
1106     dropIA i m ia@IndicesArr { .. } = m ia { end = end - i }
1107
```

1108 The only non-trivial operation is pushing an integer to the top of the stack. There are two
 1109 things that we need to be careful about: (1) if we want to push i , we actually need to write
 1110 $i - delta$ to the array, since $delta$ is logically added to all the integers in the stack; (2) we
 1111 need to restore the original content of the array after we finish our computation, where 'our
 1112 computation' is passed in as an argument m .

```
1113
1114     pushIA :: Int → M s a → M s a
1115     pushIA i m ia@IndicesArr { .. } =
1116         do oldV ← readArray arr end
1117             writeArray arr end (i - delta)
1118             a ← m ia { end = end + 1 }
1119             writeArray arr end oldV
1120             return a
1121
1122
```

1123 With these ingredients we can write our stateful implementation of *forceShifts*, which is
 1124 essentially the same as *forceShifts* before except that the data structure is changed:

```

1125 forceShiftsST ::  $Tm_S \rightarrow M\ s\ Tm$ 
1126 forceShiftsST ( $Var_S\ v$ ) = lookupIA  $v$ 
1127 forceShiftsST ( $Abs_S\ i\ b$ ) = dropIA  $i$  (addIA 1
1128 (pushIA 0 ( $\lambda ia \rightarrow Abs\ \langle \$ \rangle\ \textit{forceShiftsST}\ b\ ia$ )))
1129 forceShiftsST ( $Apps\ i\ f\ a$ ) = dropIA  $i$  ( $\lambda ia \rightarrow$ 
1130  $App\ \langle \$ \rangle\ \textit{forceShiftsST}\ f\ ia\ \langle * \rangle\ \textit{forceShiftsST}\ a\ ia$ )

```

1133 The function *forceShifts*₈ invokes *forceShiftsST* with a sufficiently large initial array (we
 1134 could also use the classic doubling trick if we do not want to pre-determine the array size):

```

1136 forceShifts8 ::  $Int \rightarrow Tm_S \rightarrow Tm$ 
1137 forceShifts8  $n\ t$  = runST \$
1138   do let  $m = 1 + n + \textit{depth}$ 
1139          $indices \leftarrow \textit{newGenArray}\ (0, m)\ (\lambda i \rightarrow$ 
1140           if  $i \leq n$  then return  $(n - i)$ 
1141           else return  $(-1)$ )
1142         forceShiftsST  $t$  (IndicesArr 0  $(n + 1)$   $indices$ )
1143
1138   depth ::  $Tm_S \rightarrow Int$ 
1139   depth ( $Var_S\ v$ ) = 0
1140   depth ( $Abs_S\ _\ b$ ) =  $1 + \textit{depth}\ b$ 
1141   depth ( $Apps\ _\ f\ a$ ) =  $\max(\textit{depth}\ f)$ 
1142                       (depth  $a$ )

```

1144 Our final normaliser is then

```

1145 nf8 ::  $Tm \rightarrow Tm$ 
1146 nf8  $t$  = let  $n = \textit{fv}\ t$  in forceShifts8  $n$  (reify7 (wnf7  $t$  (reflect7  $n$ )))

```

1148 Our normaliser is asymptotically better than or equal to the standard NbE normaliser *nf*₅
 1149 on all families of input programs. In particular, it is faster on the adversarial test that we saw
 1150 earlier: *fv* (*nf*₈ *nbeAdversarialExploit*). On this test *nf*₇ is slightly faster than our *nf*₈ because
 1151 there is not much index shifting in this test, but we can construct the following example to
 1152 differentiate *nf*₈ from *nf*₇:

```

1153 ( $\lambda x_0. \lambda x_1. \lambda x_2. \dots \lambda x_N. (\lambda y. c\ y\ y\ \dots\ y)\ x_0$ ) ( $\lambda z. c$ )

```

1154 where c is a free variable. The normal form of $\lambda z. c$ is shared for all the y -s but this normal
 1155 form is shifted by N when it comes to the context of $c\ y\ y\ \dots\ y$.

```

1159 manyShifts ::  $Int \rightarrow Tm$ 
1160 manyShifts  $n$  =  $Abs\ (\textit{go}\ n) \cdot (Abs\ (Var\ 1))$  where
1161   go 0 =  $Abs\ (\textit{foldr}\ (\lambda\_ r \rightarrow r \cdot Var\ 0)\ (Var\ (n + 2))\ [1..n]) \cdot Var\ n$ 
1162   go  $i$  =  $Abs\ (\textit{go}\ (i - 1))$ 

```

1164 This computes immediately on my machine: *fv* (*nf*₈ (*manyShifts* 10000)), while with *nf*₇ it
 1165 is much slower.

1166 The normaliser *nf*₇ (what I call NbE with shared normal forms) is known as *strong*
 1167 *call-by-need evaluation* in the literature (Biernacka et al. 2022), where ‘strong’ refers to
 1168 normalising under binders. Also, Biernacka et al. implement such a normaliser using (*freshly*)
 1169 *named variables* in values rather than de Bruijn indices, because shifting names is a no-op
 1170 (and normal forms with named variables can always be converted back to de Bruijn indices
 1171 easily). Arguably this is a nicer way to do NbE with shared normal forms than what we did
 1172
 1173

(nf_7 and nf_8) here, but I still like our solutions here because they show how far one can go with only the lazy tagging trick and careful analysis of the performance bottleneck.

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